

Practice Abstract #6

Legal and regulatory requirements shaping climate-smart land management: Practical guidance from EARTHONE's legal framework

Summary

OBJECTIVES. EARTHONE mapped key legal and regulatory requirements that affect climate-smart land management and the use of digital monitoring and decision-support tools. Practitioners operating in land-use, forestry and environmental management may need to consider EU frameworks such as the LULUCF Regulation, the EU Climate Law, CAP conditionality and Natura 2000 protections. When using technologies such as sensors, drones or AI-supported models, additional obligations may arise under the GDPR, the Data Act and the AI Act. Understanding these requirements supports better planning, reduces compliance risks and can strengthen trust when deploying new tools.

RESULTS. Amended LULUCF rules mandate that Member States increase carbon removals, rewarding carbon-positive practices while restricting activities that reduce them. Monitoring technologies trigger GDPR obligations, including transparency and the need for Data Protection Impact Assessments for personal data. The Data Act regulates sensor data sharing in collaborative farm or municipal settings. Since EARTHONE uses predictive models, the AI Act requires transparency, human oversight, and risk management. National forest and land-ownership laws further dictate permitted practices, making legal compliance a pillar of climate-smart innovation.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS. When adopting agroforestry or carbon-farming, managers must verify compliance with national rules and CAP conditionality, documenting sequestration to secure eligibility for eco-schemes or certification. Digital tool users must apply GDPR principles by collecting only necessary data and ensuring secure storage. Collaborative groups should implement data-use agreements to clarify ownership under the Data Act. For AI tools, like fire behaviour models, users must ensure human oversight and transparent assumptions. While costs include administrative time and training, benefits include reduced penalty risks and enhanced long-term resilience.

Additional information

Several factors may facilitate or hinder the practical implementation of legal requirements. Facilitators include active cooperatives, municipal authorities and advisory services that can interpret EU rules and help practitioners adjust management strategies accordingly. National CAP networks and rural development agencies can also support compliance with conditionality and eco-schemes by providing templates, training and guidance. Obstacles include the complexity of EU regulations, limited legal literacy in rural communities, differences in national interpretation, and administrative burdens linked to documentation, reporting and environmental assessments. Digital divides, such as poor connectivity, limited cybersecurity measures and restricted access to legal support, may further complicate compliance. For end-users, the key message is that legal frameworks can strengthen long-term viability by enhancing funding eligibility, reducing penalty risks, building public trust and ensuring that climate-smart land management aligns with evolving EU policies and societal expectations.

Useful links:

- [EU Climate Law overview.](#)
- [LULUCF Regulation.](#)
- [Data Governance & Data Act.](#)

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